

STRUCTURAL GLASS FIBRES FOR OPTICAL DAMAGE, CURE AND MOISTURE INGRESS SENSING IN ADVANCED REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

Advanced reinforced polymer composites (ARPC) are used within many load bearing applications; however the uncertainty of cure, damage manifestation (barely visible impact damage, BVID) and moisture ingress all lead to unknown mechanical properties and failure mechanisms. To remove uncertainty from ARPC many methods have been developed to detect damage, cure and moisture ingress however, most of these involve destructive testing or expensive component downtime with expensive expertise for non-destructive testing (NDT). The development of cure monitoring system would enable the reduction in manufacturing cost such that the component is only kept at temperature until the resin system is fully cured.

The most promising techniques for damage sensing are those which prevent component downtime. These include two types of systems; embedded sensors and self-sensing which either integrated a sensor or use the intrinsic material properties to detect damage.

Many methods have been investigated to integrate different types of sensors into composites. Most of these techniques have involved embedding a range of optical fibres:

- Intensity based sensors [1-4]
- Interferometric sensors (Fabry-Pérot) [1, 2]
- Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) [1, 2]
- Polarmetric sensors [1]

These sensors give a range of data from damage detection from fracture to strain wave detection under impact. One of the major issues of this work was the dimension of commercial optical fibres which normally have a diameter of 125µm in comparisons to standard reinforcing fibres of 5-25µm. This diameter mismatch produces problems in compressive loading producing failures in the fibres before the panel is loaded. However, work has

been done to reduce the fibre diameter of intensity based [5] sensors and FBGs to improve mechanical properties [6].

Self-sensing has been performed on both carbon and glass fibre composites. Swait *et al* [7] demonstrated the detection of BVID using the intrinsic electrical resistance of carbon fibres, whilst Fernando and co-workers have produced a series of papers covering the field of intrinsic optical sensing. The latter uses a intensity based method of detection where fibre fractures and bending losses attenuate transmitted light and consequently can be used to determine the state of panel. The system is however, limited by only being able to use modified resin systems with low RI and the imperfections in reinforcing glass fibres such as bubbles, compositional variations and un-uniform cross sectional area [8]. These intrinsic optical properties of reinforcing fibres are thought to limit the maximum transmission length.

As an epoxy resin cures the groups react together, and using infra-red spectroscopy the resonance of these groups can be monitored. Using this principle a scanned chromatic infra-red (IR) light can be projected down the fibre forming an evanescent wave in the resin; the attenuation of the wave gives a spectrum indicating which groups have reacted and continuous monitoring with respect to time shows the state of cure. This principal is known as fibre evanescent wave spectroscopy (FEWS) and has been demonstrated by Fernando [9] and Bailey [3].

FEWS however requires a fibre which can transmit in the IR. Fernando *et al* [9] gave a list of near infra-red (NIR) absorption peaks for DGEBA with various common curing agents in the range of 1159 to 2400nm.

Bailey [3] demonstrated that moisture absorption could be detected in Araldite 5052 epoxy resin using a peak at 1900 nm using chalcogenide fibres. Chalcogenide glasses have a good IR transmissions

making them ideal for FEWS but, they are complex to process and give relatively low strength fibres [3]. Hence previous work has shown that glass fibres can be used, for FEWS for monitoring of cure [9] and moisture ingress [3]. Previous work has also demonstrated that fibres can be used for damage detection. Therefore, combining the two aspects could enable a sensor to be made which can monitor both chemical and physical condition of the composite.

The aim of this work is to produce an ideal hybrid structural and sensing optical fibres for intensity based damage sensing, and also for FEWS for cure and moisture ingress monitoring. It was decided that the fibre must meet the following criteria:

- Mechanical properties suitable for reinforcement.
- Exhibit interfacial properties similar to current aluminosilicate reinforcing fibres (E-glass) enabling simple integration to composite systems.
- Similar fibre dimensions to reinforcing fibres to minimise any detrimental effects on compressive strength.
- Easy to produce fibres.
- High chemical durability.
- Low toxicity with minimal environmental impact.
- Suitability for all epoxy resin systems
- A large enough optical transmission window for FEWS for monitoring cure and moisture ingress.
- A refractive index (RI) which is greater than that of typical commercial resin system to enable intensity based optical damage detection.

For the new glass fibres to be suitable for damage sensing they must have an RI greater than that of the resin. Epoxy resins have a range of RI values from 1.55 [4] to 1.63 [10] depending on composition. Therefore the glass fibre must have an RI greater than 1.63.

To meet the chemical durability and surface chemistry criteria a silicate glass must be used. However, silicate glasses are inherently limited to transmission below $<2723\text{nm}$ due to Si-OH bonds that are formed when water is present in a silicate melt (which is usually the case) [11]. This

wavelength is within the 1159 to 2400nm range set out by Fernando.

Two approaches were investigated: use of known high RI glasses and modification of existing structural glasses. The literature indicated that niobium silicate glasses might have useful properties so the first glasses trialed in table 1 are alkali niobium silicates. Initially two potassium niobium silicates were trialed; the Li:Nb:Si composition was taken from [12] and titanium was added to further increase the RI.

Table. 1. Compositions of alkali niobium silicate glasses.

Composition	3K:3Nb :5Si	2K:3Nb :5Si	Li:Nb:Si	Li:Ti:Nb:Si
K ₂ O	30	20	38.5	38.5
Nb ₂ O ₅	30	30	15.4	15.4
SiO ₂	40	50	46.1	23.05
TiO ₂	0	0	0	23.05

The second approach was to use existing structural fibres and modify them with niobium (Nb). E-glass is characterised as an aluminosilicate with no alkali ions and hence good chemical durability. So two compositions were tested a calcium aluminosilicate with an addition of niobium and a commercial boron free E-glass [13] with 5% Nb substituted for Al. Naka *et al* [14] have reported on high dielectric constant glass fibres (H-glass) with comparable mechanical properties to E-glass hence this glass was also investigated. Lanthanum was added to H-glass as a substitution for titanium to further increase the RI. These glasses are listed in table 2.

Table. 2. Composition of niobium modified glasses.

Composition	Ca:Al:Nb :Si	E-glass - 5%Al + 5%Nb	H-glass	H-glass -Ti +La
K ₂ O	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.00
Nb ₂ O ₅	3.855	5.00	6.00	6.00
SiO ₂	41.43	56.43	50.00	50.00
TiO ₂	0.00	0.70	11.55	0.00
Al ₂ O ₃	3.855	15.73	0.00	0.00
CaO	51.40	19.42	7.50	7.50
MgO	0.00	1.96	0.00	0.00
Na ₂ O	0.00	0.61	0.00	0.00
BaO	0.00	0.00	15.00	15.00
ZrO ₂	0.00	0.00	2.45	2.45
SrO	0.00	0.00	7.50	7.50
La ₂ O ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.55

Epikote 828 (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA)) and 4,4'-Diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS) were used as the reference epoxy resin in this work due to its wide use and relatively high refractive index. Currently the authors of this paper are investigating a range of commonly used resins systems to give an overview of the range of refractive indices that need to be covered by glass fibres for damage sensing.

2. Experimental

2.1 Glass melts

Glasses shown in table 2-3 were batched using sand (99.8 wt% in purity) and reagent-grade oxides, carbonates or nitrates to produce 300g of glass. Constituents were melted in a platinum crucible at 1450°C for 1 hour followed by 4 hours stirring to produce a homogenous melt. The crucible was then removed from the furnace and left to cool until a high enough viscosity was reached to pour a block with no striations.

The blocks were cast into a steel mould and annealed at 750°C for 1 hour and cooled at 2°C/min until room temperature. Once the glass blocks had

been poured, the remaining melt was heated above the liquidus temperature and allowed to cool to a visually appropriate fibre drawing viscosity. A silica rod was then used to up draw fibres from the melt by hand as proof of fibre forming ability.

2.2 Epoxy resin samples

Epikote 828 (diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA)) and 4,4'-Diaminodiphenylsulfone (DDS) were mixed 100:30 respectively at 120°C until the DDS fully dissolved. This was then degassed at 80°C for 10 minutes and poured on to a mould released glass sheet and cured using the following schedule:

- Ramp to 120°C at 2°C/min
- Dwell at 120°C for 2 hours
- Ramp to 185°C at 2°C/min
- Dwell at 185°C for 6 hours
- Ramp to 20°C at 2°C/min

2.3 Sample preparation

Sections were cut, ground and passed through a 200µm sieve for X-ray diffraction (XRD). 3K:3Nb:5Si and 2K:3Nb:5Si samples were heat treated to further crystallise samples to enabling crystallisation peak determination. This was done using the following heating cycle:

- Ramp to 1100°C at 5°C/min
- Dwell at 1100°C for 2 hours
- Ramp to 20°C at 5°C/min

Samples for ellipsometry, UV-vis and FTIR spectroscopy were cut from the blocks and ground to parallel using a range of oxide papers and finished on one side using 6 and 3µm diamond paste and cerium oxide polishing. The back face of the samples was roughened to reduced backside reflections.

2.4 Experimental procedures

Powder x-ray diffraction XRD was performed on samples to check for any crystallinity. This was done using a Siemens D5000 XRD with a CuKα radiation at 0.4 degree per minute from 15-60 degrees. Crystalline phases were matched using PDF4+ software.

Differential thermal analysis (DTA) was performed on powdered samples by thermally cycling the samples twice using the following heating regime:

- Ramp to 1400°C at 10°C/min
- Ramp to 20°C at 10°C/min
- Ramp to 1400°C at 10°C/min

The first heating and cooling cycle was undertaken to remove thermal history from the sample. DTA was performed on samples to determine T_g and any crystallisation peaks.

Ellipsometry was performed on a Horiba-Yvon UVISEL spectroscopic ellipsometer. The raw data was used as only a single layer was present, so the data could be directly converted to RI.

UV-vis spectroscopy or Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed on samples to determine the absorption window.

Viscometry was measured using a Brookfield DV-III Ultra Rheometer with an alumina crucible and spindle. Samples were run from 1450°C to 1000°C. The liquidus point was measured using a thermal gradient liquidus furnace with a 17cm mullite “boat” crucible with a 5°C/min ramp to 1250°C and left to dwell for 24 hours. During this time temperatures were measured along the top of the crucible. After a 24 hour dwell the crucible was quenched in air and left for visual examination.

Density was measured by averaging 5 samples using a Mettler Toledo 4 figure balance with a density kit.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Glass melts and fibre drawing

The visual appearance of glass melts are given in table 3:

Table 3. Visual appearance of melts. C = Crystalline
T = Transparent

Composition	Appearance
3K:3Nb:5Si	C
2K:3Nb:5Si	C
Li:Nb:Si	T
Li:Ti:Nb:Si	C
Ca:Al:Nb:Si	T
E-glass -5%Al + 5%Nb	T
H-glass	T
H-glass -Ti +La	C

The first glasses melted shown in table 1 crystallised upon pouring blocks apart from Li:Nb:Si which was successfully poured and fibres were drawn.

Potassium niobium silicate batches could be formed into glasses upon splat quenching between steel plates however, this was unsuitable for fibre forming. The addition of titanium to Li:Nb:Si caused instant crystallisation even upon splat quenching.

All of the modified structural glasses apart from the lanthanum modified H-glass produced transparent glasses and uniform fibres with, no crystalline regions. The addition of lanthanum to H-glass caused crystallisation upon pouring and splat quenching.

3.2 XRD

XRD scans are shown in figure 2-8. Li:Nb:Si, Ca:Al:Nb:Si, E-glass -5%Al + 5%Nb and H-glass are all X-ray amorphous.

The other samples were all matched and crystalline phases are shown in table 4.

Table 4. Determined crystal phases markers correspond to markers on graphs; figures 2,3,5 and 9 respectively.

	✦	◆	▼
3K:3Nb:5Si	$K_3Nb_3O_6Si_2O_7$	$K_3Nb_8O_{21}$	-
2K:3Nb:5Si	$K_{1.8}Nb_5O_{15}$	$K Nb Si_2O_7$	-
Li:Ti:Nb:Si	$Li_{1.075}Nb_{0.625}Ti_{0.45}O_3$	$Ti O_{0.71}$	$Li Ti O_2$
H-glass -Ti +La	$Sr_{0.167}La_{4.667}(SiO_4)_3 O_{1.167}$	$Zr_{1.32}Al_{1.8}Si_{0.88}$	-

It can be seen that both potassium niobium silicate samples crystallised to form potassium niobium oxides and potassium niobium silicate phases. The addition of titanium to Li:Nb:Si caused the formation of lithium niobium titanium oxide and lithium titanium oxide.

3.3 DTA

Glass transition temperatures and crystallisation temperatures are given in table 5.

Table. 5. DTA data for glasses $\Delta T = T_x - T_g$

	T_g (°C)	T_x (°C)	T_{2x} (°C)	ΔT
Li:Nb:Si	702	943	1093	241
Ca:Al:Nb:Si	808	1246	1320	438
E-glass + 5%Nb	807	1152	1303	345
H-glass	789	990	1149	201

All glasses have relatively large differences between glass transition and crystallisation temperatures demonstrating they are all stable glasses.

3.5 Density

Table. 6. Density data for glasses

Composition	Density (g/cm ³)
Li:Nb:Si	3.217
Ca:Al:Nb:Si	3.112
E-glass -5%Al + 5%Nb	2.858
H-glass	3.779
E-glass	2.620 [15]

All of the glasses have high densities as expected especially H-glass which is 44.23% higher than that of E-glass. This factor prevents these glasses from being used as the only reinforcing fibre within a composite. However, co-mingling with other structural fibres could produce a composite with sensing capabilities with a minimal impact on the composites final weight.

3.6 Ellipsometry

Figure 2 demonstrates the ellipsometry results of the glasses and resin sample. 828 (DEGBA) was used as a reference point for the new glass fibres. Fused silica was used to check the calibration of the

instrument. The values were consistently low and thus a correction based on the fused silica values has been applied to all the data shown.

Li:Nb:Si produced a high refractive index in comparison to its density, this could be due to the effect of lithium on the glass network causing a shrinkage and consequently a high electron density resulting in a high refractive index [11]. However, it was decided to not continue with the Li:Nb:Si glass due to its use of Li which would reduce its chemical durability in comparison to the structural glasses with no alkali content.

The addition of Nb to the aluminosilicate and E-glass compositions gave an increase in refractive index as expected. However, H-glass possess a high RI more suitable to damage sensing in comparison to the other niobium modified aluminosilicate glasses which would cover other potentially higher refractive index resin systems. Consequently the following work concentrates on H-glass.

3.7 UV-vis-FTIR

Figure 1 shows a combination of UV-vis and FTIR spectroscopy absorption data for H-glass; the scan changes from UV-vis to FTIR at 3000 nm. The absorption edge is around 2700 nm and is most likely due to Si-OH bonding. However, this will allow for cure and moisture ingress monitoring by FEWS as stated in the introduction. The artefact at 860 nm is a change in the lamp used.

Fig. 1. A combination of UV-vis and FTIR spectroscopy changing at 3000nm to give the absorption edges of H-glass.

Fig. 2. Raw ellipsometry data of glasses and resin samples. A correction factor has been applied to the data using the fused silica values.

3.8 Viscometry and liquidus measurement

The viscometry data demonstrated a 1117°C ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$) log(2) fibre forming as shown in figure 3. This is slightly higher than the temperature of 1098°C reported by with Naka *et al* [14]. This could be due to Al₂O₃ impurities introduced from the crucible. The liquidus temperature for H-glass was measured at 1176°C ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). This gives a fibre forming temperature window of 59°C.

Fig. 3. Viscometry data for H-glass

4. Conclusion and future work

Preliminary work has demonstrated that H-glass is a potential candidate glass for damage/cure/moisture ingress monitoring as it is optically suitable and likely to display good mechanical properties. Further work is in progress to optimize the glass composition for fibre drawing. Once fibres are produced, the work will progress towards testing the fibres for chemical and damage sensor applications.

Fig. 4. XRD scan of 3K:3Nb:5Si

Fig. 5. XRD scan of 2K:3Nb:5Si

Fig. 8. XRD scan of Ca:Al:Nb:Si

Fig. 6. XRD scan of Li:Nb:Silicate glass

Fig. 9. XRD scan of E-glass -5%Al +5%Nb

Fig. 7. XRD scan of Li:Nb:Ti:Si

Fig. 10. XRD scan of H-glass

Fig. 11. XRD scan of H-glass -Ti +La

Figure 14 DTA of E-glass -5%Al +5%Nb

Figure 12 DTA of Li:Nb:Silicate

Fig. 15. DTA of H-glass

Fig. 13. DTA of Ca:Al:Nb:Si

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